

Expanding the Bumbuna Hydro and Solar Power Systems in Sierra Leone through Innovative Technology and Effective Financial Planning and Analysis (FINPLAN).

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Executive Summary

Access to clean energy in Sierra Leone is relatively low compared to other countries in the sub-region. Therefore, there is a need for increased private investments, effective financial planning, and economic modeling to improve access, security, and efficiency.

This report provides an overview of the expansion of the electricity sector in Sierra Leone through a combination of energy sources (Hydro and Solar) to promote renewable energy-dominated power systems. The report also assesses base capacity, the infusion of equity, and improvement of debt-equity ratios, and calculates the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR). The analysis of the available data yielded the following results:

Both the hydro and solar power systems are viable and profitable, as indicated by their positive NPV and IRR higher than the discount rate.

Recommendations:

- a. Reduce reliance on imported HFO generation to drive economic development.
- b. Increase grid generation capacity from 120 MW in 20 years and add 200 mini-grids to support energy access, efficiency, and sustainability.
- c. The increased grid generation capacity offers an opportunity to power the entire country.
- d. Sierra Leone's plan to add mini-grid generation capacity is promising.

1. Introduction

Sierra Leone is currently dealing with a severe electricity crisis marked by inadequate supply, frequent power outages, and heavy dependence on fossil fuels, particularly from Karpower. This situation is hindering economic growth, limiting access to essential services, and contributing to environmental degradation. In response, this case study explores the potential of combining a 60 MW hydropower plant with a 60 MW solar power plant to create a sustainable and reliable renewable energy solution. The project aims to increase the capacity of the existing Bumbuna hydro facility from 50 MW to 110 MW, while also adding a 60 MW floating solar installation at the same site. This combined approach is expected to improve economies of scale, leading to a reduction in energy costs and making energy more affordable for end-users. Additionally, the project could benefit from carbon credits, further enhancing its financial viability. Sierra Leone's economic development and social empowerment rely on access to clean energy from renewable sources like the Bumbuna hydro and solar energy. It is crucial to expand and transform the clean energy system in Sierra Leone to address intermittent power outages and improve sustainable access, particularly in rural communities.

Sierra Leone, like other developing countries, is dedicated to developing and expanding hydro and solar power technology and infrastructure to meet the increasing demand for clean energy. The objective is to utilize FinPlan to evaluate the economic and commercial feasibility of a mix of hydropower and solar energy, using modern infrastructure and technology to improve energy access and security.

To build a clean, cheap, and renewable energy development and infrastructure that is resilient and inclusive in Sierra Leone, effective, strategic, integrated, and mixed power sector planning is required to ensure the development of resilient and least-cost power systems that can meet current and future demands over time.

Renewables are critical for improving access to clean energy and addressing pressing climate crisis issues. Therefore, there is a need to increase clean energy production and investment in Sierra Leone. Renewable energy has the potential to provide clean energy to more Sierra Leoneans currently deprived of it.

Bumbuna Hydropower plant

Floating Solar panels

2. Methodology

The project approach relies on using relevant data. It's important to identify, define, and analyze the research approach used to gather the necessary input data for the proposed project. The primary analytical tool chosen is the FINPLAN model. However, to obtain more accurate and comprehensive results, it is crucial to have relevant data with different dimensions and parameters from the perspective of renewable energy projects. These dimensions and parameters play a significant role in the model as input factors for assessing the risks, costs, and feasibility of the project, considering the need for the required dataset.

The Bumbuna Hydropower and Floating Solar Plant project combines both Hydro and Solar Power technologies. The **Project Data** includes important parameters *such as investment, capacity, tariff, start year, construction period, and concession periods*. **Macroeconomic and Fiscal Data** are used, *including inflation (NLe), inflation (US\$), exchange rate, and tax rate*. **Financial Data** such as *debt-equity ratio, proportion of project loan, tenor, and interest rate* are also considered.

Technology	Hydro	Solar
1. Project Data		
Investment (USD million)	100	60
Capacity (MW)	60	60
Tariff (US\$ cents/KWh)	8	8
Start date	2025	2025
Construction period (yrs)	3	2
Concession period (yrs)	25	40
2. Macroeconomic/fiscal data		
SL inflation (%)	42.6	
US inflation (%)	3.4	
Exchange rate (SL/USD)	23	
Tax rate (%)	15	
3. Financial Data		
Debt/Equity	70/30	
Proportion of project loan (%)	50	
Tenor (yrs)	15	
Interest rate (%)	6	

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The FinPlan modelling approach is an analytical tool designed for the financial analysis of power projects. It can be used to design a financing package for a power project, evaluate alternative financing options, and analyse various financial uncertainties associated with a project. For this study, FINPLAN is used to evaluate the commercial and financial viability of power projects by utilizing macroeconomic, fiscal financial, and investment ratios and also recognizing standard business accounting principles for recognizing, recording, measuring, and reporting an entity's financial transactions. However, users of the FINPLAN model can manually optimize the different sources of financing and capital structure to determine the best financing plan from the given options.

3. Results

The decrease in Revenue and Dividend in **2052** can be explained as follows;

1. Solar plant lifecycle expires during that period.
2. The efficiency and capacity of the solar power panel are fully optimized during the day and in the dry season when sunlight is at its peak. This adversely affects the project's cash flows, profitability, and viability.

<i>Scenario</i>	<i>Capacity Factor</i>		<i>Project lifetime</i>		<i>Tariff</i>	<i>Tax Rate</i>
	<i>Hydro</i>	<i>Solar</i>	<i>Hydro</i>	<i>Solar</i>		
<i>Baseline</i>	45%	25%	40 yrs.	25 yrs.	8 US cents/kWh	0
<i>Scenario 1</i>	35%	20%	30 yrs.	25 yrs.	8 US cents/kWh	0
<i>Scenario 2</i>	35%	20%	30 yrs.	25 yrs.	6 US cents/kWh	15%

Source: The Researchers' analysis

In the two charts shown, below we have created a baseline case study to assess different scenarios using the capacity factor, project lifetime, tariff, and tax rates as shown in the above table. In this study, we keep one key variable constant while adjusting other parameters to understand their impact on the project's overall viability and cost. The significant drop in revenue shown in the chart is due to the end of the solar panel's life. The baseline indicates a positive NPV, while **Scenarios 1 and 2** show a decrease in IRR, indicating a reduction in capacity factor, tariff, and concession. It can be inferred that a 50% increase in equity reduces the project loan and improves the NPV and the project's financial viability. We are exploring the potential of integrating a 60 MW hydropower plant with a 60 MW solar power plant to establish a sustainable and reliable renewable energy solution. It's important to note that the project aims to increase the capacity of the existing Bumbuna hydro facility from **50 MW** to **110 MW** and add a **60 MW** floating solar installation at the same site.

Source: The researcher's analysis of the model

Baseline case: *NPP and IRR are favourable.*

Scenario 1: **No taxes, only a tariff of 8 US cents per kilowatt-hour**

Revenue and Dividends decrease sharply as a result of the end of the lifecycle of solar panels.

Source: The researcher's analysis of the model

Scenario 2: Reduce the tariff by 6 US cents per kilowatt-hour and apply a 15% tax rate. NPV and IRR are positive, indicating profitability

4. Discussion

The project is a renewable energy initiative that combines hydro and solar power, resulting in a total installed capacity of **120 MW**. Construction is scheduled to commence in **2025** and is expected to last for **2 years** for the Solar component and **3 years** for the Hydro component. The current energy tariff is approximately **8 US cents** per kilowatt-hour (KWh). The project is anticipated to be financed with **30% equity** and **70% debt**, with the debt financing comprising export credit and project loans in equal proportions. Expanding Bumbuna and Solar energy through technological innovation in Sierra Leone is crucial for increasing access to affordable, clean energy. Case studies, scenarios, and sensitivity analyses have indicated positive signs for the attractiveness and financial viability of the Bumbuna expansion project. Utilizing hydro and solar power systems is essential for providing clean power to the local and national grid.

The FINPLAN tool is being utilized to assess different financing options and analyze financial uncertainties related to the project. The analysis includes project finance, cash flows, financial ratios, operating accounts, balance sheets, and key investment metrics such as NPV, IRR, dividends, and return on equity. The results indicate positive signs for the commercial viability and shareholders' return of the proposed power systems.

Interpretation of Scenarios:

- **Baseline: 8 US cents/KWh with zero tax rate**
- **Scenario 1: Normal tariff of 8 US cents/KWh with no tax**
- **Scenario 2: Reduced tariff of 6 US cents/KWh with a 15% tax**

The findings from both scenarios indicate that the substantial drop in revenue in 2052 can be attributed to the expiration of the solar panel's lifespan. Also, the positive NPV and IRR suggesting that the project is both profitable and appealing. The proposed expansion and upgrading of the Bumbuna Hydro and Solar Power show promising signs of financial and commercial viability (NPV & IRR). The Government of Sierra Leone should promote renewable energy initiatives by providing incentives (lower tariffs and concessions) and making investments to expand grid generation to both urban and rural communities. The government should collaborate with the private sector to implement advanced hydro and solar power technology to enhance the capacity of solar panels. The proposed project aims to improve and expand energy access and affordability through the use of both

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hydro and solar energy systems. Future researchers should also consider exploring wind and nuclear power plants as alternative sources for generating, transmitting, and distributing clean, affordable, and sustainable energy.

5. Conclusion

After analysing the results of our modelling, scenario case studies, sensitivity analysis, and assumptions on the proposed floating solar and hydropower systems, it's important to note that both investment ratios, NPV and IRR, have shown positive signs but the revenue and dividend declining in the construction and operation period. The positive signs of NPV & IRR are crucial for mitigating risks and reducing project costs. The expansion of the Bumbuna hydro and solar power systems in Sierra Leone is highly necessary, supported by financial, investment, and commercial viability to improve electricity access. The proposed hydro and solar power can provide clean, affordable energy, promoting rural development and enhancing livelihoods. Together, these combined hydro and solar systems will advance Sierra Leone's journey toward clean energy resilience, security, and sustainability.

The proposed project recommends the following:

- 1) Renewable energy initiatives like this and public-private partnerships can offer innovative solutions to our energy challenges.
- 2) More public and private investments should be deployed to increase access to clean energy and develop renewables.
- 3) More solar and hydropower technology should be installed to bridge the clean energy gap, particularly in remote and undeveloped regions.

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